

NIVICOLOUS MYXOMYCETES IN UKRAINIAN CARPATHIANS

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Nivicolous myxomycetes on the territory of Ukrainian Carpathians were collected within two expeditions in May 2005 and April 2007. According to extension of snow cover, which is a necessary condition for development nivicolous Myxomycetes, the next places were selected: 1) subalpine meadow ("polonina") with a cover of *Vaccinium myrtillus* on a top of Volosyanka Mountain (Alt. 1178 m, N 48°47'18 – E 23°28'43); 2) Hoverla Mountain with widely extended spruce forest (Alt. 1226-1260 m, N 48°09' - E24°32'); 3) slopes of Khomyak Mountain with beech forest cover (Alt. 1260 m, N 48°23' - E24°30'); 4) sky complex Dragobrat (Alt. 1275 m, N 48°14' – E 24° 15'); 5) subalpine meadow with a cover of *Vaccinium myrtillus* on Sheshul Mountain (Alt. 1180 m, N 48°10' – E 24°21'); 6) slopes of Gimba Mountain (Alt. 1025 m, N 48°38'47 – E 23°17'00); 7) slopes and a top of Ozirna Mountain (Alt. 1390 m, N 48°36'34 – E 23°39'57). The main substrata were dead twigs of *Picea abies* and *Fagus sylvatica*, dead leaves, grass, living branches or living plants, etc. Expectedly, in forests conditions most of species was found on dead plant material (mainly on trunks of *Fagus sylvatica*), but in the subalpine meadows Myxomycetes were usually found on living plants (mainly *Vaccinium myrtillus*).

As a result, a total of 300 specimens of nivicolous myxomycetes were collected, from which 22 species were identified, belonging to 6 genera (*Diderma*, *Didymium*, *Lamproderma*, *Lepidoderma*, *Physarum*, *Trichia*), 4 families (Trichiaceae, Didymiaceae, Physaraceae, Stemonitidaceae), 3 orders (Trichiales, Physarales, Stemonitales), 1 class (Myxomycota). The list of species is given below (tabl. 1).

Table 1. Distribution of nivicolous Myxomycetes in different places of collecting.

Species	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Species	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
<i>Diderma alpinum</i>								<i>L. pulveratum</i>	☐	☐			☐	☐	
<i>D. meyerae</i>					☐			<i>L. retirugisporum</i>	☐					☐	
<i>D. niveum</i>		☐	☐	☐				<i>L. splendens</i>		☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	
<i>Didymium dubium</i>		☐			☐			<i>L. zonatum</i>		☐					
<i>Lamproderma aeneum</i>		☐						<i>Lepidoderma alpestroides</i>		☐		☐			☐
<i>L. carestiae</i>	☐	☐		☐			☐	<i>L. carestianum</i>	☐	☐		☐		☐	
<i>L. cristatum</i>					☐			<i>L. chailletii</i>		☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
<i>L. cucumer</i>					☐			<i>Physarum albescens</i>		☐	☐	☐			☐
<i>L. echinosporum</i>		☐	☐	☐				<i>Ph. alpestre</i>	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	
<i>L. ovoideoechinulatum</i>		☐						<i>Ph. vernum</i>	☐	☐					
<i>L. ovoideum</i>		☐	☐		☐			<i>Trichia alpina</i>	☐	☐	☐			☐	

2005 : ☐ 2007 : ☐ 2005 & 2007 : ☐

1) Volosyanka; 2) Hoverla; 3) Khomiak; 4) Dragobrat; 5) Sheshul; 6) Gimba; 7) Ozirna